

RELIANCE

Plan for Dissemination and Communication

DELIVERABLE 9.2 – WP9

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SMART RESPONSE SELF-DISINFECTED BIOBASED NANOCOATED SURFACES FOR HEALTHIER ENVIRONMENTS

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DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

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SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions set out in the Grant Agreement	
CI	EU classified — EU-RESTRICTED, EU-CONFIDENTIAL, EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444	

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RELIANCE project aims to design and develop smart response self-disinfectant antimicrobial nanocoatings based on a new range of smart antimicrobial nanoparticles. They will consist of mesoporous silica nanoparticles with metallic copper in their structure, modified with biobased bioactive compounds: Antimicrobial peptides (AMP's) based on protein containing waste streams, and essential oils (EOs) coming from non-edible plants. The antibacterial action of these additives will be adjusted to the specific application, according to the dosages and durability requirements. In this way, two alternatives to incorporate the bioactive compounds will be considered:

- The incorporation of the biobased EO into the porous substrate, to allow a controlled release (T or pH) of the bioactive compounds to the environment,
- The attachment of the AMP to the nanoparticles surface, to allow a long-term action of the bioactive compound to the environment. RELIANCE project combines contact killing and leachable antibacterial actions ascribed to the additive with the non-sticking action due to the coatings' formulation, thus providing an integral holistic solution to antimicrobial problems on different surfaces.

The nature of the coatings, their characteristics (hydrophobicity and surface roughness) and their application methods (direct deposition by cold-atmospheric plasma, high throughput spraying or selective digital printing) will be specifically designed to allow not only the microbial repelling action, but also the adhesion of the coatings to different substrates commonly found in our living environments, such as metals, plastics or textiles, and to maximize their durability (in terms of performance and antibacterial properties). Beyond the present-day possibilities of conventional chemicals, sustainability and eco design criteria will be considered in the selection of the bioactives, and in the development of the nanocoatings.

The project runs from June 2022 to May 2026. It involves 15 partners from 8 EU and 2 non-EU countries, and is coordinated by Fundacion Tekniker, Spain.

More information about the project can be found at: <http://reliance-he.eu>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Plan for Dissemination and Communication (**D9.2**) is a strategic document outlining RELIANCE consortium's communication, dissemination and exploitation vision and goals, the associated activities in their support, target audience, communication channels and key messages. It is a strategic tool, which includes the methods, approaches and communication campaigns that will be deployed to effectively build awareness about the project and raise its visibility, amplify the impact of its outcomes and their uptake by the industry, and eventually, overcome potential communication barriers with the general public at large. The Plan supports all main objectives of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation work package (WP9), namely:

- Define and implement the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy and activities,
- Integrate relevant stakeholders' engagement,
- Link RELIANCE with existing networks, projects and initiatives to promote knowledge transfer.

The Dissemination and Communication Plan is a living document to be updated twice throughout the duration of the project in order to adapt it to the project progress and continue to be a competent and relevant means of reference with regard to the planning of the communication and dissemination activities but also to evaluating their impact, during and after the lifespan of RELIANCE.

The Plan for Communication and Dissemination is an integral part of the whole communication deliverables package, that is the Report on synergies, relevant initiatives, projects and programmes (D9.3), Project website (D9.1), Exploitation Plan (D9.5) and the communication toolbox.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
A4M	Alliance For Materials
AMP	Antimicrobial Peptide
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Customer
BPR	Biocidal Product Regulation
CD	Communication and Dissemination
CI	Classified
CLP	Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substance and mixtures
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DEM	Demonstration
DG	Directorate General
DG ENV	Directorate General Environment

DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research & Innovation
DOA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECDC	European Center for Disease prevention and Control
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
ECS	European Coatings Show
EO	Essential Oils
EP	Europroject
ETIP	European Technology and Innovation Platforms
ETP	European Technology Platforms
EU	European Union
EUMAT	European Advanced Engineering Materials
EUON	European Union Observatory for Nanomaterials
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union
HADEA	Health and Digital Executive Agency
IFIB	International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISGS	International Sol-Gel Symposium
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MS	Milestone
PU	Public
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SEN	Sensitive
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SMIN	Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles
UN	United Nations
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

D9.2 PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

1. INTRODUCTION

RELIANCE is a scientifically challenging project and the understanding and acceptance of its ambitious goals and complex results by the non-scientific community, scientific peers, potential business partners or policy makers calls for an effective and well-coordinated communication and dissemination effort. A strategic plan, with clearly defined communication goals, target groups, and messages, channels and tools tailored to the respective audience group is instrumental for the project's success and will ultimately nurture support for future scientific collaboration and innovation.

This Communication and Dissemination Plan comprises all the necessary components required to ensure productive promotion of the project and distribution of its outcomes. It is linked to **task T9.1** which is effective during, and after the end of project's duration. The plan will be made available to all project partners and on the project website. Its two subsequent updates, in M24 and M48, will be taking into account the evolution of the proposed activities in the course of project's implementation and whether the set objectives have been reached so that necessary adjustments are made accordingly. A final report on the conducted communication and dissemination activities, and their impact, is envisaged to be delivered at the end of the project.

1.1. Scope

According to the definitions proposed by the EC Research and Innovation Participant Portal glossary, communication on projects "starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results", while dissemination pertains to "the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium". These definitions clearly distinguish between the main purpose of each of the above activities, with the former being predominantly informative, addressing multiple audiences, to include media and broad public, while the latter is focusing on transferring knowledge and results, enabling their use by interested stakeholders like industry partners, scientists or policy makers, thus maximizing the impact of the EU research.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan of RELIANCE adopts the above understanding in the development of a strategy that is considering both online and offline i) communication tools to reach and engage diverse user personas from the whole spectrum of the society, ii) targeted messaging to ensure wide impact at various levels of knowledge, iii) means and language that will allow accessibility to disconnected audiences in rural areas or elderly people, for example, or in other words, it is working at the level pertinent to the identified local, regional, national and international needs.

1.2. Vision and objectives

RELIANCE ambition is to create a holistic solution for healthier environments, but the world of antimicrobial nanocoatings and nanoparticles is largely hidden from our view, hence a bit abstract and unknown, representing an added challenge to the communication of research and innovation in the fields of chemistry and microbiology. Therefore, RELIANCE's vision is to spread knowledge and information about its activities and outcomes far beyond the research community, in a coherent, strategic and impactful way, led by the following key objectives:

- To inform and raise awareness about the project and its research outputs through communication tools and campaigns;
- To engage with relevant stakeholders, from civil society to policy makers to strategically selected target groups to foster wide acceptance and adoption of project's methodology and results;
- To distribute scientific information to various audiences within the academic community through peer reviewed publications, conferences and seminars;
- To cluster and create synergies with relevant EU and national projects on sustainable antimicrobial and antiviral nanocoatings for knowledge transfer and capacity building;
- To ensure exploitation of project results and follow-up on potential regulatory and business opportunities through policies and implementation.

The above objectives along with the main goal of the CD Plan - to ensure large-scale acceptance of project's results and maximize its socio-economic impact through the active involvement of cross-sectoral groups of stakeholders - will be achieved with the means of various communication and dissemination campaigns, and in compliance with the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) concept and the Open Science policy based on open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible.

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

Communication activities involve the use of mass media to share relevant information, raise awareness about antimicrobial resistance infections responsible for 110 000 deaths per year as well as the more sustainable alternatives to the currently used harmful chemicals used in the antimicrobial coatings and promote the project and its findings to various audiences, including groups beyond the project's own community. The maintenance of a consistent image, messaging tailored to the specific audiences and the translation of scientific results into layman terms lay the foundation for the broadest possible outreach of the project and opens opportunities for stakeholders' involvement in co-creation and cross-communication and dissemination activities.

Beneficiary institutions and individuals involved in RELIANCE act as ambassadors for the project and interpreters of its results. From its very beginning, the project should start promoting its goals and objectives, framework, preliminary results and any project achievement, with suitably framed messages delivered through the appropriate medium.

The CD plan of RELIANCE constitutes the reference document for all dissemination and communication implementation and is developed to respond to the following strategic questions:

- Who are we talking to – target groups of stakeholders
- What do we want to say – the messages RELIANCE partners would like to bring across
- Why are we doing it – the impact RELIANCE wants to achieve
- How do we do it – the relevant activities, tools and channels that are to be employed to reach the communicative goals, accompanied by guidelines and templates for consortium partners to disseminate and communicate project results
- When do we do it – the timing and frequency of CD activities in order for them to be most effective

The following table (Table 1) proposes a summarized view of the Communication and Dissemination Plan, which is flexible in its nature pulling together the work and information from different work packages and stakeholders’ meetings, conducted by project partners during the project and following its end.

Who	What/Why	How	
		<i>During the project</i>	<i>After the project, Legacy</i>
Policymakers Regulatory bodies	Represent RELIANCE interests and outputs to decision makers, bridge science-policy gap; Ensuring compliance and alignment to gaps and needs; Recommendations on actions.	Conferences, seminars; Dedicated publications; Webinars, Newsletter, presentations at seminars and international events including policy makers, RELIANCE mid and final conferences, social media, Website, Project video; Presentations.	Project website, project video
Public Authorities	Inform about project’s objectives and nanotechnological solution contributing to safer and healthier environment in a sustainable way.	2 workshops with brokerage events will be carried out as part of RELIANCE mid and final conferences; Social media campaigns targeting local and national stakeholders; Website, newsletter, articles, webinars	Project website, video
Interested industries (SMEs and large companies)	Inform about and collaborate for RELIANCE holistic solution for smart response self-disinfecting nanocoatings applicable to high-traffic areas, textile industry, automotive industry, etc. Includes other nanocoating solution providers.	6 project presentations, Stakeholder brokerage meetings, Reliance mid and final conferences, External events participation (i.e. congresses, trade shows), Social media, Website, project video	Social Media, Project website, project video, Joint proposal applications
Investors and businesses	Inform about and demonstrate RELIANCE solution and how it could be scaled, reused and replicated for safer, more	6 project presentations, Stakeholder brokerage meetings, demonstrations, RELIANCE mid and final conferences, External	Social Media, Project website, project video,

	sustainable and healthier environments.	events participation (i.e. congresses, trade shows), Social media, Website, project video	Joint proposal applications
Scientific community	Be informed about and feed information into the project; Knowledge exchange	Scientific Journals (5 peer review publications), Synergies building activities, stakeholder meetings, conferences, symposia, workshops; newsletter, website	joint proposal applications, project website; networking
Related EU projects in the field of antimicrobial and antiviral sustainable nanocoatings	Ensure synergies, differentiation, building on previous projects and increasing project's impact	Synergies building with 5 relevant projects and clustering activities, Articles, RELIANCE mid and final conferences, ETIP event participation, joint participation in events	Clustering initiatives, Joint proposal applications, Project website
End users and the general public	Inform and engage the public, bridge the society-science gap; show how the outcomes of RELIANCE are relevant to our everyday lives; social acceptance of needed technological solutions can lead to long-lasting impacts for citizen wellbeing.	2 workshops special content easily accessible and understandable Newsletter, 3 popular science articles in national or local media, social media curious facts campaign; public engagement campaign	Project website, social media, project video, online promotional material
The media	Inform and promote general project's objectives and results	3 Press releases, website, newsletter, 3 popular science articles	Project website Social Media

Table 1. Summary of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1. Target Audience

In the framework of the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) concept and the Open Science policy, societal actors of various walks of life, such as researchers, citizens, public authorities, non-governmental organizations, businesses, work together during the research and innovation process to align its outcomes with the needs, values and expectations of society, which could be represented through the **Quadruple Helix Innovation Model** below.

Figure 1. Quadruple Helix Innovation Model

This approach has been utilized to define the target audience within RELIANCE and several stakeholder profiles have been identified:

a. Policy and Public Authorities

In the context of RELIANCE, public actors refer to governmental agencies within public procurement, environmental management, regional development, which formulate, adopt, implement, evaluate, or change environmental and health-related policies. These might include institutions exclusively dedicated to healthcare technologies and innovation regulation, but also institutions with broader focus on citizens' social wellbeing and circular economy as well as intergovernmental organizations. Some examples are the Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA) of the EC, the funding authority for RELIANCE, DG Health and Consumers, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (DG RTD, Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV), UN World Health Organization (WHO), European Center for Disease prevention and Control (ECDC), European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) along with its Nanomaterials Working Group, member state governmental bodies, national funding agencies, supporting agencies, officials, legislators.

Nanomaterials are covered by rigorous regulatory framework that ensures the safe use of all chemicals and mixtures, like the REACH, CLP and BPR (Biocidal Product Regulation) regulations and due to concerns posed to human health, working with nanoparticles could be subjected to additional regulations in the future. Furthermore, producing, testing, approval of active substances and regulating nanomaterials requires nationally and internationally agreed tests and in vivo tests. Therefore, seeking a constant dialogue with policy makers and regulatory agencies ([European Chemical Agency](#), [European Food Safety Authority](#) and [European Medicines Agency](#)) is essential for the subsequent exploitation plan of the project. They need to be informed about the project's results from a policy perspective and be actively engaged in

providing feedback on whether project outcomes address current limitations, match the needs of the decision makers on policies affecting the use and application of nanotechnologies in terms of nanoparticles and address future needs.

b. Interested Industries, Investors, Businesses

This group comprises both SMEs and large industries and business organizations with an interest in self-disinfectant surfaces. Besides the enterprises that are part of the consortium and would be the first direct users of its results, here, RELIANCE will engage with a cross section of large companies, potential end-users, working in the field of paint and coatings, textile coating, metal and glass coatings as well as chemical suppliers, to include oleochemicals, chemical additives, coating chemicals. These are the companies that intend to commercialize the novel development, tested and validated in the respective demo work packages, which requires robust exploitation plans, risk and benefit assessments, and methodologies. They will also benefit from the networking opportunities in the project. Focused dissemination and exploitation activities are of paramount importance for this group.

Clearly, the lab to industrial scale transition of a novel research solution requires solid financial support. Therefore, starting from the second third of the project's duration, targeted communication effort towards public and private investors, banks or venture funds are to be intensified in terms of talking about and demonstrating RELIANCE solution and how it could be scaled, reused and replicated for safer, sustainable and healthier environments.

c. Research and Academia

This group is subdivided to include the applied academia and research community in the field of advanced engineering materials and nanotechnologies, and the related EU projects in the area of antimicrobial, antiviral and antifungal nanocoating technologies, to highlight opportunities for collaboration, inter-linkages and the possibility of feeding into and transferring RELIANCE results to other projects and areas (cf. Synergy Report D9.3).

Suitable scientific niches for disseminating RELIANCE results are represented through the European Technology Platform (ETPs) like EUMAT and the powered by it Alliance for Materials (A4M), the created by the EC European Union Observatory for Nanomaterials (EUON), which among other things monitors safety issues and engages in dialogue with national authorities, stakeholders and citizens, and lastly, the Joint Research Center of the EU Science Hub for Nanotechnology.

Project's progress, activities and technological developments is regularly communicated to the above noted scientific communities so as to influence subsequent usage of the outcomes. Through workshops, networking and synergy events, the engagement with them allows for quality dissemination of news

related to nanomaterials towards the broader public as their platforms and events are visited by a multitude of diverse stakeholders.

d. General Public

End users and members of the society who are not represented in any of the above featured target audience groups. Keeping them well informed, and in this way involved with the project and its deliverables, from the early stages of the activities is considered crucial for building positive public perception and follow-on social acceptance of needed technological solutions, which in turn can lead to long-lasting impacts for the citizens' wellbeing, especially in the post COVID-19 context.

In addition to the use of all one-way communication channels, the communication plan holds special attention to reaching citizens through the organization of 2 Workshops to show how the outcomes of RELIANCE are relevant to our lives as we are in daily contact with high-traffic surfaces in the public transport, hospitals, public buildings, offices, schools, elderly homes etc. To further enhance the market and public acceptance of RELIANCE products, they will be framed within the European Green Deal and Circular Economy strategy by highlighting the green synthesis of sustainable binder formulations for nanocoatings, reduced emissions of heavy metals and persistent chemicals in wastewater streams, and providing for recycling possibilities for the antimicrobial organic coatings to the treated surfaces.

2.2. Key Messages

Key messages are developed to ensure a uniform and consistent tone of voice of the project while communicating its key goals, objectives and impacts towards a more resilient society as a whole. They are distributed to all partners who have agreed on them and embedded in all communication and dissemination related to the project. Each key message communicates a specific idea and therefore resonates best with the specific target audience and context it is designed for. Along the project timeline, and circumstance dependent, the messages can change or be adapted, or certain messages could be given higher prominence than others. When applicable, the messages, being part of a local communication strategy, could be tailored to reflect the peculiarities of the home environment and audience alike.

In addition to conveying the core idea of RELIANCE, the ultimate goal of the key messages is to trigger specific action.

Message 1: RELIANCE mitigates the spread of infections (including COVID-19) and creates a healthier and more resilient society with the innovative self-disinfected antimicrobial nanocoatings with combined microbial repelling action it develops. → Target audience: a, b, c, d

Message 2: RELIANCE ensures consistent product efficiency and market demanded sustainability, with low impact on the environment through green synthesis of binder formulations, innovative bioactives and

additives from renewable resources along with energy efficient and non-toxic production. → Target audience: a, b

Message 3: RELIANCE minimizes the risk of spread of infections from harmful pathogens arising from everyday human activities. → Target audience: d

Message 4: The nanocoatings of RELIANCE kill the microorganisms by contact killing and smart bioactive leaching (EOs kill the microorganism within 5 min, avoiding the proliferation of the infections).

Sub message: The new nanocoating eliminates > 99.9 % of gram positive and gram negative bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*), *Neisseria meningitidis* and/or *E coli*; 99.9 % of viruses *influenza A virus* and *SARS-CoV-2* and a wide range of fungi such as *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium funiculosum*, *Paecilomyces variotii*, *Gliocladium virens* and *Chaetomium globosum* → Target audience: a, c

Message 5: RELIANCE improves citizens health by creating healthier living and working environment. It offers holistic solutions to people with health issues that is highly effective against a wide range of bacteria, mould and viruses and can be applied to a wide range of products. → Target audience: a, d

Message 6: RELIANCE benefits society with giving it surfaces with lasting protection against microbes. Antimicrobial surfaces in public places hinder the spreading of infections and reduce the use of harmful cleaning agents and disinfectants improving our health. → Target audience: d (specific focus on immunosuppressed people - around 6 million people live with immunodeficiency worldwide, but between 70-90% are not diagnosed).

Message 7: RELIANCE enhances EU's reputation as a public health best practice region with alleviating the effects of antimicrobial resistant infections with a new class of biocidal synergistic antimicrobial compounds as a durable and alternative solution to cancerogenic chemicals. → Target audience: a

Message 8: RELIANCE boosts research, development and innovation in the EU through innovative sustainable-by-design advanced materials and technologies enabling the EU's industrial leadership in circular economy and green transition. → Target audience: a

Message 9: Enhance economic benefits through reduction of lost hours of work due to illness. Antimicrobial resistance infections costs EUR 1.5 billion per year in healthcare costs and productivity losses. → Target audience: a, b

Message 10: RELIANCE boosts research, development and innovation in the EU in the context of circular economy by strengthening cross-sectorial cooperation along the value chain and enabling SMEs to transform their activities and business models. → Target audience: b.

For example: The use of the novel keratin-based AMPs and EOs open new Business to Business (B2B) and Business to Customer (B2C) opportunities for the engaged SME's in their respective market segments.

Message 11: RELIANCE provides business opportunities for SMEs for upscaling production, optimizing and validating the deposition of the nanocoatings ensuring their uptake by the market. → Target audience: b

Communication key words and phrases:

- antimicrobial surfaces
- antimicrobial coatings
- nanoparticles
- nanomaterials
- advanced engineering materials
- sustainable antimicrobial, antiviral and antifungal nanocoatings
- bio-based antimicrobial nanocoatings
- antimicrobial resistance mitigation
- sustainable solutions
- citizens wellbeing
- safe environments
- bio-based reliable solutions
- Optimization of antimicrobial use

2.3. Communication Tools and Channels

a. Visual Identity

Logo

The project's logo has been designed by the consortium during the proposal phase of RELIANCE and approved by all partners during the Kick-off meeting in Eibar, Spain. It consists of the project's acronym, using the Viga sans serif font, with anatomy performing well on screen, and a shield icon with particles inside, creating powerful associations of protection against potential harm, evoking a sense of safety and trustworthiness when speaking of and looking at RELIANCE.

With its green and blue colors, on the one hand, it shapes the projects' identity as clean, holistic and calm, and on the other hand, as reliable and professional. The logo is an intrinsic component of the communication strategy of the project and must be included in the marketing materials across all channels, to strengthen and complement the communication of the project's goals and brand messages.

Figure 2. RELIANCE Logo

Figure 3. Allowed variations - white logotype on logo's colors background

Graphic Charter

In addition to the logo a graphic charter has been created outlining the standards and rules regarding the communication and dissemination of the RELIANCE brand.

The purpose of the graphic charter is to provide uniformity and coherence to project's communication by supporting a consistent brand image, which ensures project's recognition and memorization by the relevant stakeholders.

All communication tools of RELIANCE should be in compliance with the guidelines set out in the graphic charter, so that the main messages are properly conveyed to the various target groups, and always in harmony with its mission and objectives.

Colors

Institutional palette

For Graphics, Design & typography . Similar shades are also accepted.

	#273879	R: 39 G: 56 B: 121	C: 100% M: 92% Y: 22% K: 8%
	#00A286	R: 0 G: 162 B: 134	C: 81% M: 12% Y: 60% K: 1%
	#231F20	R: 35 G: 31 B: 32	C: 0% M: 0% Y: 0% K: 100%

Similar shades:

	#6D6E71				
	#939598				
	#D2D2D4				

Colors

Institutional palette - secondary colors

Secondary colors are inspired by the following characteristics of RELIANCE, making the project unique:

- #5bc8dd Smart response to the environment
- #f065a2 Sustainable and economically attractive antimicrobial products
- #734fa0 Innovation through novel nanocoatings

Guidance on how to display the acknowledgment of the EU funding as well as general Word and Powerpoint templates, with all branding requisites, are also part of the graphic charter, which makes it an easy-to-use reference tool when it comes to maintaining a consistent visual identity of the project.

Stationary

Word document - Title page

Word document - letterhead

Powerpoint - Title slide

Powerpoint - slides

How to display the
acknowledgement of EU funding?

Display the EU emblem

Disclaimer

Please use the following disclaimer whenever using the funding logo:

- "Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

- "This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101058570 (RELIANCE)"

Figure 4. RELIANCE Graphic Charter

Both the Logo and Graphic Charter are available to all project partners in a shared collaborative internal SharePoint, accessible by the project partners through the Intranet section on the webpage.

b. Public Relations

The relations of RELIANCE with both the public and media are managed through the creation of attractive promotional and informational materials, such as the project brochure, online leaflet, video as well as regular press releases and an electronic newsletter. In addition to using RELIANCE own media, the general project's overview, at first, and later, the main achievements of the project and related events are promoted via the local press, with the support of partner organizations' press offices and media contacts, whenever feasible.

RELIANCE press kit is available for use to all partners and their communication needs in the project's SharePoint drive, while at the same time, it is easily accessible and downloadable by external users from the project's website (<https://reliance-he.eu/media/>), where all materials are published in English.

Marketing Materials – brochure, leaflet, A0 poster

The marketing and promotional materials within RELIANCE are designed by Europroject (EP) and comprise in their essence a print brochure, online leaflet and an A0 poster. Naturally, additional images, infographics and illustrations are adapted, designed and developed, for use on social media or offline, on an as needed basis or upon partners' request and with their input, in order to presenting the project, its objectives, expected results and benefits to end-users in a comprehensive manner.

The materials are modifiable so that at the later more results yielding phase of the project, they incorporate specific messages tailored to particular events and/or target audiences.

Brochure

The brochure of RELIANCE was created in M1 with the concept to serve as the project's factsheet foundation for any future informational derivatives for print or online communication and dissemination. The information contained therein presents a concise overview of the project, in a graphically attractive manner and non-technical language, focused on the following: the need for the research and ambition of the project, its objectives, expected results as well as consortium's composition, funding scheme, duration and contact information.

The brochure and the online leaflet are reaching out to stakeholders identified as target audience, in general. It has been designed in English, in two formats: a tri-fold material for print, which is to be distributed by project's partners during project events, national/international information days, demonstrations, visits, and an online leaflet with each partner's obligation to cooperate in its digital distribution among their respective network of contacts and media through sharing it on their own websites and social channels, as well as any other websites or social spaces of interested in the project institutions or organizations (neighborhood centers, consumer pages, blogs, professional associations, etc.).

The online leaflet is modifiable for various digital media, easily customizable to serve each partner's needs, in a proper size so that it is easily sharable across various online channels, and is multi-screen compatible.

Smart response self-disinfected bio-based nanocoated surfaces for healthier environments

COORDINATOR: Fundación Tekniker (TEKNIKER)

Microbial colonisation of surfaces forms a dangerous reservoir for pathogens contributing to spread of infections which can cause significant cost to human life and the economy at large. There is a tangible need for innovative antimicrobial coatings that are highly effective, safe, self-disinfecting, and more cost effective in killing bacteria, fungi, and viruses than the current non-biodegradable, toxic, and fossil fuel-based coatings. These new coatings will contribute to mitigating the spread of infections (including COVID-19) and creating a healthier and more resilient society while ensuring consistent product efficiency and market demanded sustainability.

OBJECTIVES

RELIANCE project aims to design and develop smart response self-disinfectant antimicrobial nanocoatings based on a new range of smart antimicrobial mesoporous silica nanoparticles with metallic copper in their structure (Cu-SMN), modified with biobased bioactive compounds. Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) based on protein containing waste streams, and essential oils (EOs) extracted from non-edible plants. This will be achieved through the following objectives:

- Development of a new class of Cu-SMN based biocidal additives with a synergistic mode of action and low impact on the environment.
- Green synthesis of sustainable binder formulations for nanocoatings - organic and inorganic.
- Optimization of cold-atmospheric plasma, spraying and digital printing deposition techniques, and nanostructuring of 3 types of antimicrobial nanocoatings, applied on chromium plated plastics, glass and stainless steel, and textiles.
- Validate the new nanocoatings as high performing and with enhanced durability through demonstrators.
- Ensuring that the proposed nanocoatings are non-toxic and sustainable, and confirm their economic value.
- Promote the novel technologies for uptake by the industry.

EXPECTED RESULTS

- At least 2 additives as novel smart response nanoparticles, easily incorporated in nanocoatings to achieve antimicrobial surfaces.
- At least 2 new sustainable nanocoating formulations easily applicable to various substrates to allow for a long-lasting antimicrobial effect of nanoparticles.
- 3 types of nanocoatings with antimicrobial effect against a wide range of pathogens, sustainable enough to inhibit colonization, without toxic active agents' migration into the environment, easy to clean and durable.
- Novel depositions to achieve nano-structuring that repels microbe adhesion.
- Recycling possibilities for the antimicrobial organic coatings so that the treated surfaces can easily be taken up in a circular economy.
- Publication of scientific papers featuring new strategies for designing and developing antimicrobial nanocoatings.

OUR PARTNERS

KEY INFORMATION

- PROGRAMME:** Horizon Europe (Resilience)
- TYPE OF ACTION:** Research and Innovation (RIA)
- DURATION:** June 2022 - May 2026
- CONSORTIUM:** 15 partners from 8 EU and 2 non-EU countries
- CALL:** CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-20: Antimicrobial, Antiviral, and Antifungal Nanocoatings
- EU CONTRIBUTION:** 4 875 569 EUR

CONTACT US

PROJECT COORDINATOR:
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<https://www.reliance-he.eu> | @reliance_he | reliance-he-project

PARTNERS

Fundación Tekniker (Tekniker)
Mater S. Coop. (Mater)
Mater Technology Centre S.Coop. (MTC)
MIRALYS (MIR)
Polyfar (POLYFAR)
Castorbar (CASTOR)

Partnership Patrons (IPATRAA):
Institut National de l'Environnement et des Risques (INERIS)
Università degli studi di Roma Tor Vergata (UNIROMA)
Politecnico Militare di Roma (POMIL)
Maite Ercio Specialized de Salze (Occidental) (IES-50)
Europroject OOO (EP)
Molecular Plasma Group (MPG)
ARÇELIK A.S. (ARÇ)
Alkora High Tech (MEXCO)

Research Organizations | Industrial Partners | Universities

PROGRAMME: Horizon Europe (Resilience)
TYPE OF ACTION: Research and Innovation (RIA)
DURATION: June 2022 - May 2026
CONSORTIUM: 15 partners in 10 European countries
CALL: CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-20: Antimicrobial, Antiviral, and Antifungal Nanocoatings
EU CONTRIBUTION: 4 875 569 EUR

CONTACT US

PROJECT COORDINATOR:
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Smart response self-disinfected bio-based nanocoated surfaces for healthier environments

COORDINATOR:
Fundación Tekniker (TEKNIKER)

Financed by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HD EA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

OBJECTIVES

RELIANCE project aims to design and develop smart response self-disinfectant antimicrobial nanocoatings based on a new range of smart antimicrobial mesoporous silica nanoparticles with metallic copper in their structure (Cu-SMN), modified with biobased bioactive compounds. Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) based on protein containing waste streams, and essential oils (EOs) extracted from non-edible plants. This will be achieved through the following objectives:

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- Validate the new nanocoatings as high performing and with enhanced durability through demonstrators.
- Ensuring that the proposed nanocoatings are non-toxic and sustainable, and confirm their economic value.
- Promote the novel technologies for uptake by the industry.

EXPECTED RESULTS

- At least 2 additives as novel smart response nanoparticles, easily incorporated in nanocoatings to achieve antimicrobial surfaces.
- At least 2 new sustainable nanocoating formulations easily applicable to various substrates to allow for a long-lasting antimicrobial effect of nanoparticles.
- 3 types of nanocoatings with antimicrobial effect against a wide range of pathogens, sustainable enough to inhibit colonization, without toxic active agents' migration into the environment, easy to clean and durable.
- Novel depositions to achieve nano-structuring that repels microbe adhesion.
- Recycling possibilities for the antimicrobial organic coatings so that the treated surfaces can easily be taken up in a circular economy.
- Publication of scientific papers featuring new strategies for designing and developing antimicrobial nanocoatings.

Figure 5. RELIANCE Brochure and Leaflet

A0 poster

A large format poster for print to be used for promoting the project at conferences, fairs, trade shows, exhibitions and synergy events. The design is in synch with the established visual identity of RELIANCE while the content shifts from objectives to mostly project's impact. The poster could be customized to different print sizes depending on the context of its use.

RELIANCE

Smart response self-disinfected bio-based nanocoated surfaces for healthier environments

The successful implementation of RELIANCE will generate as main results a range of innovative self-disinfectant antimicrobial nanocoatings, combining the microbial repelling action provided by the chemistry and physics of the nanocoating, with the antimicrobial action provided by the additives incorporated in the coatings (contact killing action of inorganic metallic copper and AMPs, and smart leaching of EO's under stimuli).

- Sustainable synthesis of nanostructured coatings to be applied in a wide range of materials by novel technologies, such as digital printing, spraying and cold atmospheric plasma
- Minimised risk of spread of infections from harmful pathogens arising from everyday human activities
- Creating a healthier living and working environment and offering a holistic solution to people with health issues
- Improve citizens' health and enhance the EU's reputation as a public health best practice region
- Enhance economic benefits through reduction of lost hours of work through illness
- Boost research, development and innovation in the EU
- Provide business opportunities especially for SMEs

Partners: 15

Budget: 5€ million

Program: Horizon Europe

Duration: 48 months

Countries: 10

<https://reliance-he.eu> | [reliance-he-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/reliance-he-project) | [@reliance_he](https://twitter.com/reliance_he)

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Figure 6. RELIANCE A0 Poster

Press Release

The press releases are the means by which important project news and milestones are communicated to the press and wider public. As WP9 leader, EUROPROJECT EP and Tekniker as coordinator draft the press releases based on project's developments and partners' inputs and publishes them on the website to be either picked up by the relevant media or distributed by partners public affairs offices to local press. At least three (3) press releases are to be released during the timeframe of the project (M2, M24 and M48). The first one has already been released in M4 and is presented below (Fig. 7).

PRESS RELEASE
15 September 2022

SELF – DISINFECTANT SURFACES FOR HEALTHIER ENVIRONMENTS – NEW EU PROJECT WORKING ON INNOVATIVE HOLISTIC SOLUTION OF SMART RESPONSE ANTIMICROBIAL NANOCOATINGS

A GREAT NUMBER OF PATHOGENIC MICROORGANISMS CAN SURVIVE FOR MONTHS ON SURFACES, CAUSING THE TRANSMISSION OF A WIDE RANGE OF INFECTIONS, WHICH ARE CONSIDERED TO BE ONE OF THE MAJOR SINGLE CAUSES OF DEATH WORLDWIDE. ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANT MICROBIAL INFECTIONS ALONE ARE RESPONSIBLE FOR AN ESTIMATED 110,000 LIVES LOST (OECD HEALTH REPORT 2016) AND 1.5 BILLION EUR IN HEALTHCARE COSTS AND PRODUCTIVITY LOSSES PER YEAR.

Currently existing antimicrobial coatings raise concerns related to their antibiotic resistance, complex chemical synthesis, toxicity, non-biodegradability and extremely low sustainability in terms of product performance and environmental protection. The new Horizon Europe interdisciplinary project RELIANCE addresses the growing need for innovative antimicrobial coatings that are highly effective, safe, self-disinfecting and removing bacteria, fungi and viruses in a more efficient cost/performance ratio than the presently used petrochemical-based ones.

„Beyond the present-day possibilities of conventional chemicals, RELIANCE aims to design and develop smart response self-disinfectant antimicrobial nanocoatings with an antimicrobial action that is adjusted to the specific application. In this way, RELIANCE will contribute to having a healthier and more resilient society towards microorganisms, by mitigating the spread of infections and ensuring the health and well-being of citizens“

Miren Blanco, RELIANCE Coordinator and senior researcher at Fundación Tekniker

An Innovation Contributing to Society

The project's ambitious objective to shift from harmful chemicals to a novel class of coatings will be achieved through a new range of antimicrobial copper doped mesoporous silica nanoparticles (Cu-SMIN) modified with non-toxic bioactive compounds such as antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) coming from protein containing waste streams, and essential oils (EOs) extracted from non-edible plants, both functionalized to respond respectively to temperature and pH changes.

RELIANCE supports the transition to a circular economy through employing green synthesis of sustainable binder formulations for nanocoatings, reduced emissions of heavy metals and persistent chemicals in wastewater streams, and providing for recycling possibilities for the antimicrobial organic coatings to the treated surfaces.

The consortium of RELIANCE consists of 15 partners from 8 EU and 2 non-EU countries, to include research organizations, universities, SME and large industry partners. The project with a budget of € 5 million was launched in June 2022 and will end in May 2026.

For more information
Senior researcher Miren Blanco, miren.blanco@tekniker.es

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 <http://reliance-he.eu>

Figure 7. RELIANCE first Press Release

The electronic newsletter of the project is considered a powerful, high-conversion and cost-effective marketing tool. In addition to spreading the word about RELIANCE, it contributes to building a database of interested in the project results contacts that can become part of an overall stakeholder engagement database, even for future projects.

RELIANCE newsletter is sent to subscribers six times throughout the duration of the project, the first one starting in M8. It will include project's overview, reports on first conducted meetings, important announcements regarding social media and the launch of the website as well as partners' presentation. The content of the subsequent issues will take into account things as follows:

- events regarding project's progress and results
- dates, details, stories regarding project related conferences, meetings, webinars or publications
- project-related news, new initiatives, liaisons
- synergies with related projects, programs and initiatives.

All partners are encouraged to participate in generating content for the newsletters. Europroject (EP) is responsible for coordinating the work, collecting contributions from members, editing and distributing the newsletter. In order to reach the maximum potential audience, the consortium partners are invited to further distribute the newsletters to their professional contacts, preparing grounds for potential collaborations regarding results exploitation and/or joint applications in next projects.

Everybody can subscribe free of charge to the newsletter from the project's website where it would be published as well, in downloadable format.

Compliance

The RELIANCE newsletter will be designed in full compliance with GDPR. The email footer will display the sender's address and will offer an unsubscribe/opt out button. The first newsletter is under preparation.

Figure 8. RELIANCE Newsletter – concept

Video

A short introductory video (2-3 min) will be produced by EUROPROJECT EP post M6 to facilitate project awareness building, boosting its visibility and raising social interest in the research subject of RELIANCE. The video will be published on the website, shared on social media and through the newsletter, on partners' websites and digital media, and will be played at events.

An animated infographic of the explanatory video genre will illustrate in simple terms the project's objectives and complex activities so that they are understood and accepted by a non-specialized audience, that is society at large.

Video concept

Figure 9. RELIANCE animated video concept

Videos are an essential communication tool which is becoming increasingly popular and outstanding the other forms of communication with the highest engagement rate with the audience. The video will also include adapted to the narration subtitles so that it is accessible and comprehended by everyone and anywhere.

c. Website

RELIANCE website is the main avenue of all communication activities of the project. The RELIANCE domain was acquired in July 2022 (<https://reliance-he.eu>) and the website was brought live in the end of September, fully designed and developed by EUROPROJECT EP as WP9 leader, in collaboration with Tekniker, as coordinator, and the rest of the project partners. The website is updated and maintained throughout the project's lifespan, to include 2 years after its end. This ensures access to the knowledge and data accumulated during the project to partners, key stakeholders and the public at large even beyond the timeframe of the project.

The website of RELIANCE appears in all promotional materials, both print and online, and constitutes a space for regularly communicating outputs, achieved milestones, and publishing official results.

The website aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Build awareness and understanding about project’s mission, work activities, objectives and results;
- Ensure visibility of the project;
- Enhance the impact of the project through timely and accessible dissemination of its results;
- Enable effective communication between the project and external stakeholders, media and the public;
- Wide promotion of the project through easy access to the portfolio of informational and branding materials;
- Enable synergies and engagement with similar projects, programs and initiatives through relevant content, a prerequisite in itself for sharing and exchanging knowledge and best practices;
- Facilitate the exploitation of the project’s results.

Its sections include information about the project, overview of the consortium, description of the project expected results (including public deliverables once approved), demonstration sites overview, news and events and topic related short articles (blog posts), project e-newsletter, video, communication kit for the media and social media links.

Figure 10. RELIANCE website's navigation, cover photo, title and key information

The website is described in detail in deliverable **D9.1 Project Website**.

Project partners’ are continuously encouraged to make reference to the project on their own websites too.

d. Social Media

Social networks are the place where we connect with our audience most, the place where the conversation happens, and when used strategically, they become an efficient tool for reaching a variety of stakeholder groups. The dynamic nature of the information exchange there turns them into a suitable host to real-time

information sharing, announcements of important events, synergy actions, reports, briefs as well as live streaming of webinars, speeches, interviews, etc. In this sense, social media contributes directly to the following objectives:

- Build awareness and increase visibility
- Trigger interest in the topic and subsequently support it through sharing news with both expert and non-expert audience
- Multiply the impact through engagement in relevant subject specific community groups
- Build an expert voice by commenting and sharing opinion on trending topics and issues in the field
- Promote knowledge, activities, benefits and outcomes generated during and after the project's lifespan
- Enhance project positioning through engine search, image search, local search
- Engage with the target audience by two-way interactions through surveys, polls, public discussions and invitations to project's events

Due to the quick turnover of news in the digital social environment, it is essential for the project's communication success to post content regularly vs. ad hoc or sporadic activity. For this reason, a Content Publishing Calendar is created for project's partners to plan their content contributions for both social media and website, with the aim to post at least once a week and share relevant content generated by another user/contact once a week.

RELIANCE consortium has decided to use Twitter and LinkedIn for social networking. Twitter is considered as one-to-many broadcast networks which has a conversation pace much faster than any other social media. A diverse community of scientific, research and business organizations hang out there, either institutionally or individually, which makes it a good medium for promoting RELIANCE news and results, especially in hashtag campaigns and as threaded content. The handle of RELIANCE in Twitter is [@reliance_he](https://twitter.com/reliance_he) and the activity of the project there will increase with its progress and results generation.

Figure 11. Twitter Account of RELIANCE

LinkedIn is the professional social network of RELIANCE where it connects with similar projects, creates events, and again, performs cross-sharing and reposting of news and important project information from its other channels. The project's name in LinkedIn is [@reliance-he-project](#).

Figure 12. LinkedIn Account of RELIANCE

Both social media accounts of RELIANCE are managed by Europroject, with the active support and inputs of all partners who are regularly reminded to follow and share the accounts, and posts, on their personal and institutional profiles as well as to recommend correlated organizations, projects, initiatives and events

that the project can start following in order to build a solid network of stakeholders and induce higher engagement rates through conversations and re-posts.

The information posted on the social media account is done in a consistent and coherent manner, using the defined above (cf. 2.2. Key Messages) messages, project's keywords and phrases as hashtags as well as the appropriate tagging of partners, collaborators and EC authorities for greater visibility.

Twitter and LinkedIn icons are integrated in the footer of the website with a call to action to visitors to follow us. It is planned to add social media buttons in the News section of the website, allowing readers to easily share the published content, such as events, news or articles, on Twitter and LinkedIn.

e. Other

Publications

Publications regarding RELIANCE scientific work and outputs are essential for meeting the project's objectives. Research partners are committed to present papers at international conferences and peer review scientific journals, giving priority to open access editions to increase visibility and quotation rates.

Joint papers and other publications on innovative nanotechnology research issues, written together with colleagues from related EU projects would not only disseminate the results internationally but would enhance the esteem of the partnership and unambiguously demonstrate the collaboration drive of the EU-funded research for stronger European economies and technological and innovation progress, improving our lives.

Keeping track of the number of own generated publications but also of such that quote project's authors or refer to the project's outcomes is an important value for a later on assessment of the dissemination impact of RELIANCE.

Events

Throughout the project's lifetime, the consortium members are expected to attend a considerable number of events related to RELIANCE and the research fields it is positioned in, either as participants or organizers. The Communication and Dissemination Plan focuses mostly on the external activities given the internal coordination and consortium meetings are considered mostly a management tool rather than means for communication and dissemination of project's goals, objectives and results to its users.

Some types of events that are meant to be organized and attended by the partners are international conferences, fairs, trade shows and exhibitions, workshops for the general public with brokerage events during the mid and final conferences of the project as well as coordinated joint and synergy events with other related programs, projects and initiatives that are elaborated upon in **D9.3 Synergy Report**. In the post COVID-19 times, it should also be taken into account, that events might be in-presence, online or hybrid, each with their own interractional requirements and marketing specifics.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

The strategic communication, dissemination and exploitation approach adopted within the project is aligned with the general and specific objectives of the respective activity, with messages, channels and format, tailored to the relevant target groups, local context and timing. Table 1 highlights a summarized version of the proposed communication and dissemination strategy.

Besides being linked to Task 9.1, the implementation of the CD Plan is also linked to task 9.2. *Communication and Dissemination Campaigns*, which is dedicated to the implementation, coordination, and evaluation of the communication activities in accordance with the delineated CD plan (D9.2, 9.4, 9.7) and commences with the launching of the website and social media accounts of the project. It is led by Europroject EP and is further connected with D9.8 *Final Report of Communication and Dissemination Activities*.

3.1. Communication Strategy

The main objective of RELIANCE is to design and develop smart response self-disinfectant antimicrobial nanocoatings based on the antimicrobial action provided by a new range of antimicrobial copper doped mesoporous silica nanoparticles (Cu-SMIN), modified with non-toxic bio-actives (with smart leaching and contact killing actions towards microorganisms) combined with the microbial repelling action of nanocoating formulation; and validate them as safe, sustainable, durable and resistant to usage conditions in three high added-value and demanding industrial applications: automotive interior parts, frequently touched home appliances and protective textiles.

The communication strategy is entirely in support of this objective by launching informational campaigns from the very start of the project when albeit the scarcity of results, the first six to twelve months are dedicated to project's promotion by reaching out to society as a whole, by establishing synergies with external bodies such as national/international associations, projects and platforms.

The first communication wave of RELIANCE employs as its vehicle the **website and communication toolbox** for a general introduction of RELIANCE, its ambition correlated with defining the societal need for such research, the main approaches and methodology involved, specific objectives, expected results and overall impact across the whole spectrum of life. The main goal of this first wave is hence, brand awareness but also sparking curiosity in what is next. The second and the third communication waves are designed to gradually move down stakeholders to the middle and bottom of the marketing funnel of the project, from engagement and consideration phase, when the larger focus would fall on dissemination activities, to the adoption and advocacy phase, with communication activities targeting predominantly the exploitation possibilities within RELIANCE.

3 social media campaigns in Twitter and LinkedIn will be organized to give RELIANCE relevant, direct, and immediate connection with stakeholder groups, especially during initial activities. *Discover RELIANCE* is the proposed name for the first (M1 – M12), awareness building social media campaign. The second one,

Get into the Lab, unveils the first results and tangible outputs of the project (M18 – M36) and the last one, *For healthier environments*, targets application case studies and exploitation opportunities for the industry, funding and government authorities (M36 – M48 and after).

Horizon Europe social media guide for EU funded R&I projects will be adopted in the implementation of the above-described campaigns, including the search tool for EU related projects and initiatives for mentions and tagging in order to boost visibility and broaden the reach.

Keywords and hashtags to be used in social media:

antimicrobial surfaces
antimicrobial coatings
nanoparticles
nanomaterials
advanced engineering materials
sustainable antimicrobial, antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal nanocoatings
bio-based antimicrobial nanocoatings
antimicrobial resistance mitigation
sustainable solutions
citizens wellbeing
safe environments
bio-based reliable solutions
Optimization of antimicrobial use

Emojis:

RELIANCE communication strategy wishes to spread project’s activities and outcomes beyond the research community. Being directly related to the health and well-being of citizens in the aftermath of COVID-19, the communication strategy will be paying special attention to reach all citizens through the organization of **2 Workshops** to show and explain how the outcomes of RELIANCE are relevant to our everyday lives while we are in contact with high-traffic surfaces in public transportation, hospitals, public buildings, schools, elderly homes and related to health workers wearing protective textiles as well.

In the Monitoring and Assessment Section, the CD plan features some quantitative KPIs regarding the communication activities (number of visits in the webpage and social media, number of

talks/presentations, videos uploaded, number of events, attendance to public engagement events, etc.) to monitor the progress and efficiency of the plan. In the case of low impact data detected at an early stage, pertinent corrective actions will be set up like adapting the messages, tone of voice and language, frequency and medium of publications. The monitoring plan includes also periodic partners' reports on results of communication actions.

3.2. Dissemination Strategy

The dissemination activities begin with the advancement of the project towards its first achieved results that benefit the EU citizens or transfer knowledge to stakeholders that can best make use of it. All partners are responsible for spreading the word about the outcomes of their work, thus making them available for future research, interdisciplinary interactions and uptake by specific audiences, including but not limited to: scientific community, industrial and other commercial actors (SMEs), policymakers, professional organizations, public authorities.

The objectives of the current dissemination effort are defined as follows:

- Raise awareness about project results in the segments of advanced engineering materials, chemical and oleochemical groups, regulatory and decision-making authorities, public health-related institutions;
- Promote investment opportunities with investors or commercial partners;
- Spark interest in RELIANCE as a holistic solution adding economic and health value to the European societies;
- Publish and promote the research results delivered by the project;
- Understand and protect intellectual property rights during collaborations with industry participants;
- Raise awareness about the wider benefits of adopting RELIANCE solution, beyond its original focus;
- Maximise general public visibility of the project's results and achievements;

The main channels and tools to achieve these objectives are presented below:

Online Media

Twitter and LinkedIn campaigns – the second and third social media campaigns described in more detail above: *Get into the Lab* (M18 – M36) – aims to trigger deeper interest to engagement with project's results and *Holistic solution for healthier environments*, (M36 – M48 and after) – sharing application case studies, popular articles, blog posts to target industry, investors, public institutions with potential exploitation opportunities.

Continuous dissemination to the media includes ***3 press releases***, also shared on RELIANCE's digital social accounts. ***Popular articles*** are planned to be published in sector-specific blogs or popular science magazines, for example the magazine associated with the European Coating Show with readership of influential level, with the prospect to accelerate the deployment of RELIANCE new technologies. A

newsletter starting in M8 until the end of the project is sent to the pool of interested subscribers generated from the subscription form on the website to keep them posted about the latest news and developments. The public deliverables of RELIANCE as well as any other materials sent created by the consortium partners to bring visibility to project's outputs and achievements are published on the **website** and openly accessible.

One opportunity which should be taken into account with the advancement of work is the generation of a success story that is to be published on own channels, reposted on partners' websites and further promoted via some of the European Commission's free-of-charge channels: Cordis Results in Brief, CORDIScovery podcasts, Research & innovation success stories, Horizon Magazine or during events such as the R&I Days, subject to coordination with the Project Officer.

If despite the best effort for dissemination and exploitation no uptake happens one year after the end of the project, the exploitable results will be made visible on the Horizon Result Platform.

Publications

Publishing about project's research and the results it entails is essential for meeting the project's dissemination objectives among the scientific community and fellow researchers. The partners will publish at least **5 peer-reviewed publications** of significant results in high impact, open access scientific journals.

Journal / Magazine	Description	Impact Factor
Coatings	Coatings (ISSN 2079-6412) is an international, peer-reviewed and open access journal devoted to the science and engineering of coatings, thin and thick films, surfaces and interfaces. Coatings publishes original research papers and brief communications that report on the latest finding of research together with review papers that systematize the remarkable points on the state of the art. https://www.mdpi.com/journal/coatings/about	2.8
Bioactive Materials	Bioactive Materials is an international, peer-reviewed research publication covering all aspects of bioactive materials. The journal welcomes the submission of research papers, reviews and rapid communications that are concerned with the science and engineering of next-generation biomaterials that come into contact with cells, tissues or organs across all living species. https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/bioactive-materials	14.5
Molecules	Molecules is the leading international, peer-reviewed, open access journal of chemistry. Molecules is published semimonthly online by MDPI. https://www.mdpi.com/journal/molecules	4.4
Nanomaterials	Nanomaterials (ISSN 2079-4991) is an international and interdisciplinary scholarly open access journal. It publishes reviews, regular research papers, communications, and short notes that are relevant to any field of study that involves nanomaterials, with respect to their science and application. Thus, theoretical and experimental articles will be accepted, along with articles that deal with the synthesis and use of nanomaterials. Articles that synthesize	2.1

	<p>information from multiple fields, and which place discoveries within a broader context, will be preferred. There is no restriction on the length of the papers. Our aim is to encourage scientists to publish their experimental and theoretical research in as much detail as possible. Full experimental or methodical details, or both, must be provided for research articles. Computed data or files regarding the full details of the experimental procedure, if unable to be published in a normal way, can be deposited as supplementary material. https://www.mdpi.com/journal/nanomaterials/about</p>	
Adsorption Science and Technology	<p><i>Adsorption Science & Technology</i> is a peer-reviewed, open access journal devoted to studies of adsorption and desorption phenomena, which publishes original research papers and critical review articles, with occasional special issues relating to particular topics and symposia. https://www.hindawi.com/journals/ast/about/</p>	2.425
Polymers	<p><i>Polymers</i> (ISSN 2073-4360) is an international, open access journal of polymer science. It publishes research papers, communications and review articles. <i>Polymers</i> provides an interdisciplinary forum for publishing papers which advance the fields of (i) polymerization methods, (ii) theory, simulation, and modeling, (iii) understanding of new physical phenomena, (iv) advances in characterization techniques, and (v) harnessing of self-assembly and biological strategies for producing complex multifunctional structures. https://www.mdpi.com/journal/polymers/about</p>	4.3
Trends in Analytical Chemistry	<p>The articles in <i>TrAC</i> are concise, critical overviews of new developments in analytical chemistry, which are aimed at helping analytical chemists and other users of analytical techniques. These critical reviews comprise excellent, up-to-date, timely coverage of topics of interest in analytical chemistry, such as: analytical instrumentation, biomedical analysis, biomolecular analysis, biosensors, chemical analysis, chemometrics, clinical chemistry, drug discovery, environmental analysis and monitoring, food analysis, forensic science, laboratory automation, materials science, metabolomics, pesticide-residue analysis, pharmaceutical analysis, proteomics, surface science, and water analysis and monitoring. https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/trac-trends-in-analytical-chemistry</p>	12.296
Microchemical Journal	<p>The <i>Microchemical Journal</i> is a peer reviewed journal devoted to all aspects and phases of analytical chemistry and chemical analysis. The <i>Microchemical Journal</i> publishes articles which are at the forefront of modern analytical chemistry and cover innovations in the techniques to the finest possible limits. This includes fundamental aspects, instrumentation, new developments, innovative and novel methods and applications including environmental and clinical field. https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/microchemical-journal</p>	4.821
Talanta Open	<p>Talanta Open is a gold open access, peer-reviewed companion journal to Talanta that publishes original research papers, short communications, and reviews in all branches of pure and applied analytical chemistry. https://www.elsevier.com/journals/talanta-open/2666-8319/subscribe</p>	

Table 2. An indicative, non-exhaustive list of European and International related journals

Some of the accumulated scientific outcomes will also appear in the following international scientific journals: Journal of the American Chemical Society, Journal of Physical Chemistry B, Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation, Biophysical Journal, Journal of Molecular structure, Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics, Materials, Biointerphases, ACS Nano, International Journal of Nanomedicine.

Open Access

By following the ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’ principle, RELIANCE consortium ensures the required intellectual property rights maintenance by the partners and authors while granting at the same time immediate open access to the scientific publications. When appropriate, and in support of its dissemination and exploitation action, RELIANCE will avail from the assets offered by the European Commission and enable open access to relevant project research results with gold access (under Creative Commons open licenses) through the Open Research Europe platform (ORE), complementary to the above listed specialized DOA journals. Research data will also be shared on trusted repositories on shared HESS-SO server powered through the MS SharePoint web interface, when it comes to internal to the consortium data, and publishable data in an open-data repository, such as ZENODO, for example. Other publishing platforms that are considered to be utilized for the dissemination and exploitation of the results are ViXra, Chemical Sciences Article Repository, EOSC.

The toxicity tests with rats in RELIANCE will be appropriately disaggregated by sex so as to obtain separate results while studying the different response per this indicator. In this way, the disaggregated findings will be separately reported and disseminated to specialized journals, along with mainstream research magazines.

Partners are encouraged to speak about the project in public venues and to publish results obtained throughout the project. In preparing speaking material and/or publications partners focus on their own work and results.

Any proposed publication relating to the project are sent to the Coordinator and all other Parties at least 30 days before publication date. Any of the Parties may object to the publication within 15 days whenever there is an assessment of intellectual property rights infringement or the publication includes sensitive information.

All partners have the legal obligation to properly acknowledge the funding received by the European Union on all communication and publications. An important element with this regard is the European Union emblem and the funding statement, which must be displayed prominently on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels and other communication products. This is further elaborated in Section 5. *EC Acknowledgment Requirements*.

Events

- ***Two workshops with brokerage events*** - carried out as part of RELIANCE mid (M30) and final conferences (M48). With an eye to exploitation possibilities, they will target professionals from the automotive, textile, appliance and medical industries, R&D and end-users aiming to provide information and knowledge exchange on the state-of-the-art exemplified in the solutions developed within the project and the sector as a whole.

- **RELIANCE final conference** - to coincide with the third communication wave and summarise the implemented activities, share the results and foster the uptake of developed novel solutions.
- At least **6 presentations** by key project representatives at selected scientific conferences, congresses, symposia, exhibitions, trade shows, fairs to facilitate the wide exposure of the project's outputs.
- **International Conferences and Events** - a non-exhaustive, suggestive list of relevant European and international event is presented in the table below:

Name	Description
Coatings and Interfaces Conference	Series of events bringing together scientists and technologists from academia and industry, encouraging the involvement of excellent early-stage investigators. Participants have the opportunity to share their most recent findings with a focus on the areas of Coatings and Interface Science and Technology.
Coatings Science International	This conference is intended for researchers and research managers, active in the field of Science and Technology of Coatings both from industry and academia. Polymer and paint chemists, as well as surface and interface scientists, formulators, designers and industry policy makers will find in this conference a broad platform for exchanging the latest developments of their disciplines. https://coatings-science.com/
International Sol-Gel Conference	Brings together leading academic scientists, researchers and research scholars to exchange and share their experiences and research results on all aspects of Sol-Gel Science and Technologies. It also provides a premier interdisciplinary platform for researchers, practitioners and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns as well as practical challenges encountered and solutions adopted in the fields of Sol-Gel Science and Technologies. https://waset.org/sol-gel-science-and-technologies-conference-in-november-2023-in-london
Annual biocontrol industry meeting	Worldwide event for the biocontrol industry. Last edition took place live in Basel where more than 1550 participants from 53 nations were able to network together, face to face, as well as listen to inspiring presentations and panel discussions. https://www.abim.ch/
International Sol-Gel Society	ISGS is an international, interdisciplinary, not-for-profit organization whose primary purpose and objective is the advancement of sol-gel science and technology. ISGS aims are both to represent the particular needs and aspirations of the international sol-gel community and to support this sol-gel community. https://www.isgs.org/

ENoLL events	<p>The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) is the international, non-profit, independent association of benchmarked Living Labs.</p> <p>Living Labs are real-life test and experimentation environments that foster co-creation and open innovation among the main actors of the Quadruple Helix Model, namely: Citizens, Government, Industry Academia.</p> <p>ENoLL facilitates knowledge exchange, joint actions and project partnerships between its historically labelled +480 members in Europe and worldwide.</p> <p>Its aim is to promote the Living Labs concept in order to influence EU policies, enhance Living Labs and enable their implementation at a global level. https://enoll.org/about-us/</p>
International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy	<p>The International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy, organized by Italian Circular Bioeconomy Cluster SPRING, Innovhub-SSI and Federchimica-Assobiotec.</p> <p>IFIB brings together the main world bioeconomy stakeholders, who gather to discuss and present the latest updates in the new economy based on renewable, biological resources. https://ifibwebsite.com/</p>
European Coatings Show (ECS)	<p>The gathering of the coatings and paint industry. Trends and technologies covering all aspects of the production of paints, coatings, sealants, construction chemicals and adhesives. https://www.european-coatings-show.com/</p>
European Bioplastics Conference	<p>Europe's leading business and discussion forum within the global bioplastics sector. More and more brands and manufacturers are embracing the potential of biopolymers, and policy makers are increasingly streamlining their efforts to create frameworks that benefit the growth of sustainable bio-industries. https://www.european-bioplastics.org/events/eubp-conference/</p>

Table 3. RELIANCE suggested international conferences

Networking

As comprehensively elaborated in the *Report on Synergies with relevant Initiatives, Projects and Programs (D9.3)*, networking activities enhance the dissemination of project results to a broader interest audience, increase the visibility of the members and foster learning from, and building upon, other projects' findings and experiences. Some initiatives seen as beneficial for cooperation and extended dissemination of RELIANCE outcomes are for example, the EU NanoSafety Cluster, Nanotechnology Industries Association, European Union Observatory for Nanomaterials (EUON), European Technology Platforms (ETPs) like EUMAT, and other European Technology & Innovation Platforms (ETIP) that are recognized as suitable niches to present the scientific achievements of RELIANCE, as they are visited by the target stakeholder groups. For a detailed outline of these as well as other synergy and collaborative opportunities, read the Report (D9.3).

Dissemination after project's end

RELIANCE social media accounts and website, including the private partners' space will keep being functional 2 years after the project concludes, to provide access to the acquired knowledge and accumulated data. The project data will also be available in selected and consolidated repositories (cf. Data Management Plan). The synergies established during the timeframe of RELIANCE can expand beyond its length through an ongoing interaction with the identified related organizations, networks, initiatives and similar EU-funded projects (Task 9.4), enabling a robust stakeholder community with entities having an interest in using RELIANCE antimicrobial solutions, cooperating on a range of future joint dissemination actions, or up taking RELIANCE results to common funding applications or future technological collaborations. As far as the joint proposal application is concerned, one year before the final project meeting, partners will focus on compiling a joint Research and Innovation (R&I) agenda to discuss and plan the endeavor. The final outcomes of the joint R&I agenda are expected to be operationalized in new projects in the field of antimicrobial, antifungal and antiviral nanocoatings, expanding on the approaches, technologies and outcomes of RELIANCE.

3.3. Initial Exploitation

Given the societal, economic and scientific significance of RELIANCE, a separate Exploitation Plan will be developed as deliverable D9.5, linked to Task 9.3 Exploitation tools and activities. The exploitation plan for the project's technological solutions would allow for the large-scale exploitability of RELIANCE results and would contribute to maximizing its impact beyond its initial focus through enabling sustainability, usability and replicability of RELIANCE project research outputs and concept as a whole. The potential patenting of RELIANCE technologies will be explored to grant visibility to project's products and solution long after its completion.

In brief, the exploitation strategy adheres to the following underlying objectives:

- Define an IPR and data management strategy,
- Build a roadmap to foster large-scale exploitability of RELIANCE outcomes and draw the project's business plan and
- Explore further synergies with relevant projects and initiatives.

In M24 a ten-year open access roadmap for antimicrobial, antiviral, and antifungal nanocoatings will be developed, as organic to RELIANCE. A common business plan will be developed as part of the exploitation strategy to ensure the longstanding availability of the cost-effective solutions and the endurance of the technologies developed within RELIANCE. The Exploitation Strategy will be finalized in M48.

4. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

Review measures and evaluation mechanisms are required to keep the dissemination and communication plan in vigor. Its effectiveness is assessed against the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) set in the Grant Agreement, and whenever serious discrepancies are ascertained, necessary adaptations are made to the DC Plan in order to keep abreast of the project's goals and its successful implementation.

4.1. Key Performance Indicators

Per RELIANCE Grant Agreement, the project has defined the following KPIs:

Channel/Medium	Purpose	KPIs	Main Target Group
Website (M4) One-way communication	Main avenue of information about the project; Educates about the research topic through blog posts; Disseminates its findings; Provides contact information for interested stakeholders.	10000 website visitors throughout project's lifetime; 1000 visitors/month in the last year of the Project; kept active 2 years post project's end.	All
Social Media (M1) Two-way communication	Connecting with target audience; Informs and disseminates results; Real time information exchange; All partners contribute.	>500 followers; 3 Social Media campaigns	All
Communication Materials (M1) One-way communication	Branded in accordance with the visual identity of the project. Promote and inform; Updated in line with the key messages and communication waves.	>1.000 material distributed	Relevant stakeholder groups; All
Press releases (M2) One-way communication	Brand awareness; Raise Interest in project and its results; Highlight business uptake opportunities.	at least 3 press releases	Media and general public
Newsletter	Informs, promotes, disseminates results;	at least 6 Newsletters	Interested stakeholders

Could be two-way	Promotes events and RELIANCE participation		through subscription form
Articles One-way communication	Inform, promote, educate	At least 3 popular science articles	Specific Stakeholder Groups
Scientific publications One-way communication	Dissemination of significant results in high impact open access scientific journals	5 peer-reviewed publications; 150 specialised stakeholders reached	Scientific community
Presentations Two-way communication	Wide exposure of the project's outputs at scientific conferences, congresses, symposia, exhibitions, trade shows, fairs	At least 6 presentations	Researchers, Academia, Public Institutions, Government Bodies, Industry
Workshops (M24 and M48) Two-way communication	Involve citizens and inform about project's activities for better acceptance of RELIANCE technology; Q&A session	>200 stakeholders (100/workshop)	Citizens, general public
Workshops with brokerage events (M30, M48) at mid and final conference Two-way communication	Dissemination of results Focus on Exploitation	15 interested industrial partners reached 2 workshops with brokerage events at mid and final conference	Industry Investors
Synergies/Networking Two-way	Knowledge transfer; Boost impact through joint communication/dissemination	5 related projects; 2 Networks/Working groups	Research Community ; Regulators ; Industry
Video (post M6) One way communication	Spread information on social media and the web, illustrating project's objectives, activities and impact	1 video – 2 -3 min; 1000 views	Consumers

Table 4. RELIANCE communication strategy KPIs

4.2. Monitoring Dissemination Activities and Event Participation

To facilitate an accurate monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication activities and to gain better understanding of the impact of the performed actions, the partners of RELIANCE consortium are asked to file a report every 6 months, using the created for this purpose Communication and Dissemination Tracker (number and type of stakeholders reached in events, articles published, flyers distributed, events attended, etc.). The information gathered via the tracker will be used during the regular reporting periods in the EC portal. It is populated with data by each WP leader and sent to WP9 leader and project coordinator. A separate reporting template is provided for the scientific publications.

RELIANCE Dissemination and communication activities											
Type of dissemination and communication activities	Number of Events	Description	Estimated Number of persons reached								
			Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Industry	Civil Society	General Public	Policy Makers	Media	Investors	Customers	Other
Organisation of a Conference											
Organisation of a Workshop											
Press release											
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)											
Exhibition											
Flyer											
Training											
Social Media											
Website											
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)											
Participation to a Conference											
Participation to a Workshop											
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop											
Video/Film											
Brokerage Event											
Pitch Event											
Trade Fair											
Participation in activities organized jointly with other EU project(s)											
Other											
Total Funding Amount Used	€	-									

Figure 13. RELIANCE Dissemination and Communication Tracker

Furthermore, an event reporting template is developed for partners to provide information regarding the activities they have been involved in to represent RELIANCE project, either as participants or organizers. In addition to reporting the type, location, dates and topic of these events, the average number of participants and the interest groups they are affiliated with are also monitored in order to keep track of the progress the communication and dissemination objectives are reached with.

Some of the tracked data is listed below, as follows:

- Number of scientific papers with name and impact factor of the journal
- Number of paper downloads and number of quotations
- Number of attended conferences and exhibitions
- Number of Workshops
- Number of presented presentations/posters
- Number of event attendees
- Videos produced and number of video views
- Social media posts and engagement rate on partners' pages and accounts

All partners should save evidence of the activities conducted. In the case of events, these could be photos taken from events, registration sheets and/or presentations.

The regular monitoring of the activities leads to properly assessing the planned activities and a timely identification of potential gaps or discrepancies to readjust communication if necessary. It also brings about the possibility to see which are the actions with the biggest impact on the stakeholders (both in quantitative and qualitative terms) and intensify on them.

Naturally, the communication and dissemination reporting from partners facilitates the future updates of the plan as well.

4.3. Website and Social Networks Monitoring

Website's metrics, statistics, trends, and the impact of each activity performed on the website are analyzed by RELIANCE via Google Analytics, on a regular basis. Reports on various performance indicators will be prepared to inform project partners of website's performance, such as:

- o Unique users count visiting the website
- o Average visit time and bounce rate
- o Languages and geographic locations of visitors
- o Number of page views and average page views per visit
- o Top landing page and bounce rate for different pages

Google Analytics data will be collected every 3 months and reported to the consortium at the progress management meetings. Respective adjustments will be made to improve users' experience if required.

The Insights tools of LinkedIn and Twitter accounts will be utilized to collect analytical information on the profile of RELIANCE followers as well as the engagement rate in terms of reactions, comments, shares, recommendations. This information would equip partners with a better understand what content works best in RELIANCE messaging resonating with the target personas as well as other factors like most appropriate timing of post, frequency, communication style and type of content.

4.2. Management

a. Roles and Responsibilities

The WP9 leader, Europroject EP takes responsibility for the steering and implementation of WP9 tasks and in collaboration with Project Coordinator, Tekniker and all partners has prepared this Dissemination and

Communication Plan. It is EP’s continuing responsibility to keep track of it throughout the project and provide the necessary updates (M24 and M48), following all partners inputs during the regular 6-month project meetings. Partners active involvement in the communication and dissemination of the project is critical for achieving its general and communicative objectives as well as CD plan’s alignment the exploitation goals.

As partners in a EU-funded project, consortium members commit to regularly creating content for RELIANCE’s social media, website and newsletter, to engage stakeholders and inform them proactively about the progress of their work activities, and later on - the achieved results. In an effort to facilitate content contribution, a calendar planner is created. Each partner is responsible for providing a blog-post-like article for the website, social media or newsletter, with relevant images, for their assigned week in the calendar.

Figure 14. RELIANCE Content Planner

b. Communication Waves and Deliverables

WP9 is a horizontal work package which runs during the lifespan of the 48-month project. As mentioned earlier, the communication and dissemination endeavor unfolds in three waves, each with its strategic focus and objectives. An illustrative summary is proposed below while a more detailed elaboration is found in Section III. Implementation.

Figure 15. RELIANCE Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Waves

Deliverables of high quality are essential to the success and continuing impact of the project. All WP9 deliverables are available to the public and are accessible long after the project's completion. The table below lists the deliverables in WP9 – title, description, lead beneficiary, type, dissemination level and due date.

Deliverables and Milestones								
WP No	Del No	Title	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Nature	Dissemination Level	Est. Del. Date (annex I)	Status
WP9	D9.1	RELIANCE Project Website	The website will be a key communication vector to ensure the dissemination of the	EP	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	Public	30 Sept 2022 (M4)	Submitted
WP9	D9.2	Plan for Dissemination and Communication	Strategic document including the consortium's communication, exploitation and dissemination goals, targeted audience, main messages and the strategy	EP	Document, Report	Public	30 Nov 2022 (M6)	Submitted
WP9	D9.3	Report on synergies with relevant initiatives, projects, and programmes	Report including the activities carried out to establish synergies with other initiatives. first version	EP	Report	Public	30 Nov 2022 (M6)	Submitted
WP9	D9.4	Plan for Dissemination and Communication (2nd version)	An update to the strategic document including the consortium's communication, exploitation and	EP	Report	Public	31 May 2024 (M24)	Pending
WP9	D9.5	Initial Exploitation Plan	The exploitation results report will outline the various exploitation activities and the	EP	Document, Report	Public	31 May 2022 (M24)	Pending
WP9	D9.6	Report on synergies with relevant initiatives, projects, and programmes (2nd version)	Report including the activities carried out to establish synergies with other	EP	Report	Public	31 May 2024 (M24)	Pending
WP9	D9.7	Plan for Dissemination and Communication (3rd version)	Final updated to the strategic document including the consortium's	EP	Document, Report	Public	31 May 2026 (M48)	Pending
WP9	D9.8	Communication and dissemination final report	Document including includes all communication, engagement, dissemination and exploitation actions.	EP	Report	Public	31 May 2026 (M48)	Pending
WP9	D9.9	Final Exploitation Plan/Results Report	The exploitation results report will outline the various exploitation activities and the	EP	Report	Public	31 May 2026 (M48)	Pending
WP9	D9.10	Report on synergies with relevant initiatives, projects, and programmes. Final version	Report including the activities carried out to establish synergies with other	EP	Report	Public	31 May 2026 (M48)	Pending
WP9	MS 9	Launch of project's website	Website up and running	EP	Report	Public	30 Sep 2022 (M4)	Pending

Table 5. List of RELIANCE WP9 Deliverables

c. Intellectual Property

All Consortium partners are contributors to the dissemination and communication activities under WP9 and as such they use their own networks as detailed above, for the following purposes:

- Identifying and informing about dissemination opportunities (e.g., events, publications, etc.),
- Providing relevant information and documentation to enrich the project website,
- Posting news and project results in social media

The dissemination of the project's results should not be expected to cause intellectual property rights or copyright issues to RELIANCE partners. To ensure this, all partners are duly aware about the content of each dissemination related to their activities. In the unlikely case of copyrights infringement, partners can refuse the dissemination of their own outputs.

5. EC COMMUNICATION REQUIREMENTS

As a beneficiary of the EU Horizon Europe programme, project partners hold the legal obligation to acknowledge the received EU funding and display the EU emblem in all communication materials.

How to display the acknowledgement of EU funding

Display the EU emblem

The European Union emblem and the funding statement must be displayed prominently on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels and other communication products.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Use a Disclaimer

Use the following disclaimers whenever using the funding logo:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive

Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Although not required, the Grant Agreement number could also be added:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No. 101058570 (RELIANCE).”

Horizon Europe social media related guidance on the EU acknowledgment will be available soon.

The information contained herein is also available in the project’s Graphic Charter.

6. CONCLUSION

This first edition of the Dissemination and Communication Plan of RELIANCE lays strong foundation for building general awareness about the project and its mission, and trigger interest in its first outcomes that is gradually growing into a continuing engagement with the achieved progress and developments. It is conceived with a vision to be built upon during the second, result yielding phase, while reinforcing dissemination activities to highlight the outputs and possibilities for their exploitation. The key messages are conveyed through actively utilizing digital and offline communication channels, networking opportunities and demonstrations and validation of the results at the specifically designated industry sites. The planned events provide for the occurrence of both unilateral and bilateral communication, with the latter being more user engaging and materialized in the social media and during citizens workshops. The CD plan aims to build RELIANCE prominent reputation of an innovative and holistic solution for healthier environments and its success depends on the collective participation and contribution of all partners.

It is important to highlight that this Plan is not complete without the Report on Synergies with relevant Initiatives, Projects and Programmes (D9.3), Project Website report (D9.1) and the Exploitation Plan (D9.5) since the outlined activities in all of these four documents are tightly interrelated and therefore, mutually influence, one way or another, their final outcomes, impact and ultimately, successful accomplishment.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

Deliverable 9.2 is developed in accordance with the provision outlined within the following related documents:

- RELIANCE Grant Agreement,
- RELIANCE Consortium Agreement Nr. 101058570.

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	RELIANCE Grant Agreement	RELIANCE Partners' Space
2	RELIANCE Consortium Agreement Nr. 101058570.	RELIANCE Partners' Space